

Injection Screw Effect on Nickel-Coated Graphite Fiber Composites for EMI Shielding

Chao-Chang A. Chen¹, Yi-Lung Chou², Wei-Lien Ni², Ming-Sheng Huang³, Cheng-I Teng³

¹Associate Professor, Department of Mechanical Engineering,
TamKang University, Taipei, Taiwan, R.O.C.

²Graduate, Graduate Institute of Mechanical Engineering
TamKang University, Taipei, Taiwan, R.O.C.

³PIM Lab., Victor Taichung Machinery Works Co.
Taichung, Taiwan, R.O.C.

KEYWORDS: Nickel-Coated Graphite (NCG) Fiber, Electromagnetic Interference (EMI)

ABSTRACT

This paper presents an injection screw blending effect on RTP-299AX77373A Nickel-Coated Graphite (NCG) fiber composites for preventing electromagnetic interference (EMI). The experimental materials and processing parameters are shown as Table 1.

Table 1. Materials and Processing Parameters

Materials	
.matrix material	Nylon 6
.fiber material	Nickel-Coated Graphite (NCG)
.fiber content and length	15 wt% and 6mm
Screw geometries and machine parameters	
.screw diameter	36mm
.compression ratio	2.27
.screw speed	100rpm
.barrel temperature	220~270°C
.injection machine	VS-100, Victor Taichung Machinery Works Co.

Injection barrel was designed with three removable windows, as shown in Fig. 1, for sampling composites of blending analysis in feed zone, compression zone and metering zone of injection screw. The windows were covered with S45C steel blocks and sealed with asbestos for leakage protection of molten composites. Injection barrel was heated up to the set temperatures, and screw injection process started until screw reached the metering volume then injection machine power was shut down. Simultaneously liquid nitrogen was sprayed against barrel to freeze molten composites immediately.

Experimental results of solid granules of Nylon 6 and NCG fibers were dispersed in the feed zone of screw, as shown in Fig. 2. In the compression zone of screw, as shown in Fig. 3, the matrix of Nylon 6 was melted and blended with NCG fibers to create a conductive network. At this stage the molten Nylon 6 and NCG fibers are not compound tightly. In the metering zone of screw, the Nylon 6 and NCG fibers are compound tightly, each fiber overlapped closely and NCG fiber density was high in the unit volume, as shown in Fig. 4.

From the experimental results, RTP-299AX77373A NCG fiber composites are blended and compounded well inside the screw. For applying on computer and communication products, it could create a strong conductive network for preventing EMI.

Fig. 1: Illustration of Injection Barrel with Removable Windows for sampling composites

Fig. 2: Illustration of RTP-299AX77373A NCG fiber composites in Feed Zone

Fig. 3: SEM photographs of RTP-299AX77373A NCG fiber composites in Compression Zone

Fig. 4: SEM photographs of RTP-299AX77373A NCG fiber composites in Metering Zone

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors wish to thank National Science Council in Taiwan, Republic of China under grant number NSC 86-2622-E-002-015 for financial support and Mr. Simon Lu, RTP Co. of Taiwan for his support.

REFERENCES

1. Huang-Lung Hung, Chao-Chang A. Chen, C.B Lin, C. H. Liu, Tung-Han Chuang "Shielding Effects of Different Aspect Ratio of Aluminum Flakes in Conductive Plastics for Injection Molding Processes", 11 TH International Conference on Composite Materials, Australia, July 1997, pp. 254.
2. Huang-Lung Hung, Chao-Chang A. Chen, C.B. Lin, Ming-Sheng Hung, "Visible Mold Design with Compound Fan-Gating System for Applications of Plastics Composite Materials in Preventing Electromagnetic Interference", Proceeding of the Fourteenth National Conference of the Chinese Society of Mechanical Engineers, Taiwan, Nov. 29-30, 1997, pp482-489.
3. Yi-Lung Chou, Chao-Chang A. Chen., C.B. Lin, Huang-Lung Hung, Ming-Sheng Huang, "Flow Visualization of a Compound Fan-Casting System for Injection of Plastics Composite Materials in Preventing Electromagnetic Interference ", The Fourteenth Annual Meeting of the Polymer Processing Society (PPS-14), YOKOHAMA, JAPAN, June 8-12, 1998, pp.146-147.